

COMMUNITY RENEWAL AND EXPRESSION OF ARTISTIC CULTURE

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Abstract

This article talks about the importance of artistic culture in the process of social renewal, development of all areas of spiritual life in harmony with national and universal values, important changes in all areas of artistic culture in the system of spiritual changes, ideological, artistic and aesthetic research.

Key words: society, spiritual life, artistic culture, artistic-aesthetic values, national and universal values, human thinking, worldview, principles of living, artistic-aesthetic traditions, folk artistic crafts, music, architecture, painting, sculpture, artistic crafts, decoration art, film, theater, television.

Increasing the position and status of national and universal values in the life of our society is an objective necessity of strengthening independence. For this purpose, objective conditions have been created for the radical renewal of spiritual culture in essence and content, these socio-political and economic factors form the basis of spiritual change and development, and at the same time, free thinking, democratic and civil culture, as well as the artist's worldview, his social activity, has a serious impact on the establishment of new ideological-methodical, creative-aesthetic views in the field of artistic culture.

Renewal is a purposeful, comprehensive, at the same time, complex and conflicting process that represents the needs and interests of society and people. As a result of it, a wide way is opened for quality changes in all spheres of social life, at the same time, the creative possibilities of each person expand, and the conditions for its realization are created. "Without making people believe in the need to renew and change the society," wrote the First President of the Republic of Uzbekistan I.A. Karimov, "proceeding in practice on the path of reform without changing the driving forces and attitude to values, evidence reasons, especially the establishment of a new society it is impossible to introduce completely new relations" [1].

Renewal of society actually begins with directing human thinking, worldview and living principles to higher goals and enriching them with content. Philosophically, the processes of renewal include the integration of socio-political, economic, cultural, ethical, organizational spheres, the expected changes will lead to concrete consequences, their direct and gradual connection with the era, and, finally, the perception of these changes as a historical necessity by man and society. and implies recognition.

Various forms of ownership that create a new social consciousness and thinking in society, real opportunities that provide democratic values, strong social policy, education of a perfect person, application of the principle of "transition from a strong state to a strong society", increasing role of non-governmental organizations, in turn, artistic culture updating, affecting the change of its functions.

The relationship between the reforms implemented in our republic and the artistic culture has a dialectical character, and on the one hand, it represents the processes of national identity awareness, attitude to heritage, artistic and aesthetic traditions, folk art crafts, scientific, cultural and creative associations, restoration of historical truth. On the other hand, it has a positive effect on the independent functioning of culture.

The achievement of national independence creates ample opportunities for the development of all spheres of the spiritual life of society in harmony with national and universal values. As a result, the internal and external factors of the development of modern Uzbek artistic culture were placed on a solid spiritual foundation.

Today's Uzbek artistic culture is diverse in composition and includes dozens of fields such as fiction, music, architecture, painting, sculpture, artistic crafts, decorative arts, cinema, theater, television, folk art, and at the same time creating, distributing, and assimilating artistic values. includes the world of related material objects, a system of artistic tools and methods.

Since artistic culture is the most active sphere of spirituality, it constitutes a special type of production of spiritual blessings. Its nature is such that every artistic creation creates a strong spiritual satisfaction from free creativity in the true sense. Artistic creativity encourages a person to recreate the new, creative, miraculous spiritual world, thus creating a sense of satisfaction not only in its subject, but also in others.

The uniqueness of this process is evident in the novelty, originality, originality of the created artistic gifts, and in this aspect, it fascinates the subjects of perception. Also, these blessings are materially manifested in the form of works of fiction and visual arts, architectural examples, and in turn, like other objective phenomena, they become "far away" from their creators and take a strong place in the life of society.

The peculiarity of creativity is that some of its examples take place in the form of performance, for example, in singing, acting, etc. So, let's say, "the published book has an important feature that is not dependent on the will of the author, but is related to his fate," writes scientist Abdulla A'zam, "the book now seals the presence and absence of the author's talent, both the truth and the lie." preserves, becomes a witness to his honesty as an author, as well as to the crookedness of his hand" [2]. So, the artistic activity itself happens as its product.

Products of artistic activity, values - all this is the result of spiritual activity, a set of views on life, man, nature, beauty, art, culture, skills. These artistic values are the product of a person's life activity, his work and his ability. For example, an art book, a work of art, examples of practical art are not just simple objects, they reflect the spiritual world, ideal, dreams, goals, and aesthetic needs of a writer, artist, folk craftsman. These together make up the artistic universe.

Spiritual-ideological processes in independent Uzbekistan, primarily based on the principles of the idea of national independence, have an effect on the emergence of a new artistic-aesthetic way of thinking, on the correct determination of the ideological directions of all types of modern artistic culture, on the way to the manifestation of new creative potential, and the deepening of the scope of artistic research. The ideas of re-perception of traditional, historical, cultural and spiritual-ethical values in the systems of artistic culture, such as elegant literature, architecture, painting and applied decoration, music and performance art,

art cinema, folk hobby, folk art, television, and the levels of renewal in a unique way is in progress.

The high position of each nation in the world is determined to a certain extent by the development of its culture and art, and the attitude of the state to culture, in turn, shows the level of spiritual development of the society. Consequently, "any society cannot imagine its future without developing and strengthening its spiritual potential, spiritual and moral values in the minds of people" [3].

In the years of independence, the state's sponsorship of spirituality in general, and artistic culture in particular, serves as a political basis for qualitative changes in the field of national art and national artistic thinking. As a result of the state's concern for spirituality and economic and legal measures, our national art, which is the main field of our artistic culture, has entered the right path of development.

What brought art to the forefront of social life in the conditions of independence was that it had the opportunity to communicate with the passing era, live with the admirer, to think freely and realistically about the updates and changes in all spheres of social life, complex problems. The processes of artistic reconstruction of the historical past, awareness of national identity and culture took the form of an impressive spiritual basis that drives the types of artistic culture, and the historical theme began to take the lead in creative processes.

Thanks to independence, our national art has become a part of the world artistic scene with its own values. It seems that there is a real opportunity for artistic culture to develop and reach the world level, and its range of activities and possibilities, along with traditional types of entertainment, classical music, architecture, artistic decoration and crafts, show the harmony of Eastern and Western cultures. has expanded, research in the art of cinema has been consistently continued and is being continued. At the same time, it should be admitted that there are still no artistically and ideologically high films created in this field that meet the high spiritual and aesthetic requirements of our people, such as "Tahir and Zuhra", "Alisher Navoi", "Ulugbek Star", which received world recognition.

National architectural examples rising in our country serve to form a modern aesthetic environment. The architectural art of the cities of Samarkand, Bukhara, Khiva, and Margilon became even more beautiful due to their anniversaries. The latest technologies of construction and design are creatively used in the unique combination of tradition and modernity, in the basis of the national architectural development strategy.

The ideology of independence united the team of directors, playwrights and actors of the theater art more firmly, ensured that the relations between artistic dramaturgy and the theater, between the theater and the audience, were based on national and universal values. Such changes are also taking place in the fields of art cinema, television, visual arts, and architecture.

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